

USE OF NEBULIZER THERAPY IN CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND CARDIOVASCULAR COMORBIDITY

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Abstract. *Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is characterized by persistent and usually progressive airflow limitation associated with various risk factors, the main one being tobacco smoking. The increasing role of this pathology among the causes of morbidity and mortality is well known. It should be noted that in recent years there has been a greater understanding of the complexity of this disease in terms of an integrated clinical assessment of severity, pathophysiology and relationship with other pathologies. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is a disease of the second half of life and a typical COPD patient suffers from an average of 4 or more concomitant diseases and every day about a third of patients take from 5 to 10 different drugs [5, 6]. In this regard, the significance of concomitant pathology for the course of COPD is important.*

Keywords: *the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), drug beroduat, an anticholinergic ipratropium bromidum, an agonist of beta-blockers, FenoterolumBromidum, introduction an inhalation way –the nebulizer.*

Introduction. The scale of the problem of the combination of COPD and CVD is largely determined by the prevalence of each of these pathologies separately and the fact that these diseases have much in common. COPD and CVD have common risk factors, the main one of which is tobacco smoking. Despite adequate pharmacotherapy in the treatment of COPD, it still remains one of the important causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide, including in Uzbekistan. CVD is the most common comorbid pathology in patients with COPD. According to the data obtained in a clinical study, the risk of developing CVD is 2 times higher in patients with severe and extremely severe COPD than in smokers without signs of COPD. The indicators of pharmacotherapy are very low compared to other diseases. Although the lungs are considered the main target organ for the smoking factor, it is well known that other systems are also affected by smoking, in particular, the cardiovascular system [10-12]. In addition, decreased pulmonary function is closely associated with an increased risk of developing heart failure [13–15], myocardial infarction [16], and atrial fibrillation (AF) [17]. Other common risk factors for COPD and CVD include age and poor lifestyle habits (physical activity, nutrition, etc.).

The main pathophysiological disorder in COPD is expiratory airflow limitation,. Broncho-obstructive syndrome is characterized by a combination of bronchospasm, edema (inflammatory or non-inflammatory genesis) of the bronchial mucosa, as well as increased production of bronchial gland secretion. According to J.C. Hoogetal (1968), small airways (SAT) with a luminal diameter of less than 2 mm are a zone that makes a significant contribution to the development of airflow limitation in patients with COPD. Traditionally used basic inhalation drugs for COPD have relatively large particles - about 3.5-5 μm and therefore, they are not able to equally effectively

affect all parts of the respiratory tract (RT) and especially the finely dispersed pathways (FDP). Considering that this is considered as the main site of pathological changes in COPD, today it is relevant not only to develop the creation of a drug but also to target the delivery of the drug to the distal parts of the bronchial tree in patients with COPD. The GOLD (Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease - Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease) program of 2011 proposes to prescribe long-acting inhalation drugs to patients with moderate to severe COPD for the prevention, reduction of symptoms and exacerbations.

According to foreign studies EPOCH and EPOCH-O-CHF, it was found that 11 million patients have signs of CHF, of which 3.4 million have a clinical picture of the disease corresponding to III-IV functional class (FC) according to the New York classification, the rest with various concomitant diseases (Konstam M.A. Progress.).

One of the problems encountered in patients with a combination of CHF and COPD is associated with the use of beta-blockers (BB) in pharmacotherapy. Since one of the side effects and contraindications of BB is bronchospasm, narrowing of peripheral vessels due to the effect of these drugs on beta 2-adrenergic receptors.

Although in the works of Likhtmat Zh.Kh. et al. it was found that the use of BB in patients with COPD who have suffered a myocardial infarction reduces the risk of mortality in patients by 40%, but in this situation it is better to prescribe selective BB. According to foreign studies EPOCH and EPOCH-O-CHF, it was found that 11 million patients have signs of CHF, of which 3.4 million have a clinical picture of the disease corresponding to III-IV functional class (FC) according to the New York classification, the rest with various concomitant diseases (Konstam M.A. Progress.).

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Objective: The main objective is to prevent relapses and study the effectiveness of prescribing nebulizer therapy in patients with chronic bronchitis, bronchial asthma, concomitant diseases of coronary heart disease, chronic heart failure, hypertension. COPD is associated with the use of beta-blockers (BB) in pharmacotherapy of these diseases.

Materials and methods: The study included 50 patients of different sexes, diagnosed with chronic obstructive bronchitis, moderate to severe bronchial asthma with concomitant coronary heart disease, CHF, hypertension. Of these, the first control group consisted of 10 patients with moderate to severe chronic obstructive bronchitis with concomitant coronary heart disease, CHF, hypertension. They received antihypertensive therapy: ACE inhibitors perindopril 2 mg per day, bisoprolol 2.5 mg, Thrombo ASS 100 mg, 2.4% ephyllin solution - 5 ml in 0.9% physiological sodium chloride solution intravenously and the antihistamine drug zodak 20 drops 2 times a day.

The second group consisted of 10 patients with moderate to severe chronic obstructive bronchitis with concomitant coronary heart disease, CHF, hypertension, who received antihypertensive therapy and the bronchodilator drug berodual in the form of a spray through the respiratory tract 2 times a day. The third group included 20 patients diagnosed with chronic

obstructive bronchitis with concomitant diseases of coronary heart disease, chronic heart failure, hypertension. The patients received antihypertensive therapy and the bronchodilator drug berodual using a nebulizer 3 times a day, daily for 7 days. The combined drug berodual contains the anticholinergic agent ipratropium bromide (250 mcg) and the beta-blocker agonist fenoterol bromide (500 mcg). Under the influence of this drug, bronchodilation occurs due to blocking cholinergic parasympathetic innervation and stimulation of b₂-adrenoreceptors. Fenoterol stimulates b₂-adrenoreceptors located on the smooth muscle cells of the bronchioles and causes rapid bronchodilation. In addition, as a result of the increase in the concentration of adenosine monophosphate under the influence of b₂-agonists, not only does the smooth muscles of the bronchi relax, but also the speed of the epithelial cilia increases and the function of mucociliary transport improves

Direct or indirect cholinergic stimulation causes activation of the secretory function of the submucosal glands and goblet cells of the respiratory tract mucosa and contributes to increased bronchial obstruction in COPD. Long-acting anticholinergics improve patency in the peripheral parts of the bronchopulmonary system by limiting the secretion of bronchial mucus, as they bind to muscarinic cholinergic receptors for a long time and their central properties are practically lost. With prolonged use, they clearly improve the ventilation function of the lungs, inhibit reflex bronchoconstriction, are well tolerated by patients, and do not cause side effects. Such a drug is a combination drug - berodual, which has a pronounced bronchodilating effect due to the action of the drugs included in its composition fenoterol and ipratropium bromide. All patients underwent clinical, laboratory, biochemical, and instrumental studies (blood pressure measurement, electrocardiography (ECG), spirometry, and chest X-ray). Direct or indirect cholinergic stimulation causes activation of the secretory function of the submucosal glands and goblet cells of the respiratory tract mucosa and contributes to increased bronchial obstruction in COPD. Long-acting anticholinergics improve patency in the peripheral parts of the bronchopulmonary system by limiting the secretion of bronchial mucus, as they bind to muscarinic cholinergic receptors for a long time and their central properties are practically lost. With prolonged use, they clearly improve the ventilation function of the lungs, inhibit reflex bronchoconstriction, are well tolerated by patients, and do not cause side effects. Such a drug is a combination drug - berodual, which has a pronounced bronchodilating effect due to the action of the drugs included in its composition fenoterol and ipratropium bromide. All patients underwent clinical, laboratory, biochemical, and instrumental studies (blood pressure measurement, electrocardiography (ECG), spirometry, and chest X-ray).

Results. In the first group of patients receiving antihypertensive therapy and a solution of ephyllin with the antiallergic drug zodak, an improvement was noted on the 1-2 day, in the second group of patients receiving antihypertensive therapy and the drug - berodual spray by inhalation, the effect occurred within 15 minutes and the condition of the patients improved, an improvement in well-being was noted on the 2-4 day, in the third group of patients receiving hypotensive therapy and berodual by inhalation using a nebulizer, the effect occurred within 10 minutes, shortness of breath disappeared, cough became less, the condition of the patients improved. A decrease in blood pressure was noted, hemodynamic blood parameters improved. The use of a nebulizer inhaler contributed to the rapid penetration of the drug to the small bronchi, causing bronchodilation, improving sputum separation. Spirometry studies using peak flowmetry in the first group showed

- in 4 men aged 51 ± 4.2 years, with an average height of 171 ± 5 , it is equal to 470 ± 9 (l/min), in 2 women aged 53 ± 3.5 years with a height of 155 ± 15 , it is equal to 380 ± 8 (l/min).

In the second group of patients, compared with the first group, spirometric indicators in 4 men aged 50 ± 3.3 years, with an average height of 170 ± 5 , it is equal to 520 ± 9 (l/min), in 3 women aged 53 ± 8 years with a height of 160 ± 12 , it is equal to 430 ± 6 (l/min). In the third group of patients - 4 men aged 50 ± 13 years, average height 170 ± 5 equals to 600 ± 4 (l / min), 3 women aged 53 ± 8 years with a height of 156 ± 8 equals to 530 ± 6 (l / min). at the age of 49 ± 4.2 (M \pm m) Compared with the control group, the condition improved: normalization of blood counts, spirometry was 2 times faster.

Conducted instrumental studies showed in the control group of patients with LVH was noted in 42.8%; HR 75 ± 0.42 per min., in the second group 34,6%, HR 74 ± 0.4 per min. and in the third group 28.3%, HR 63 ± 1.33 per min., respectively. The systolic and diastolic blood pressure indicators in the first group were 145 ± 0.33 and 89 ± 0.2 mmHg; 1140 ± 0.4 and 89 ± 0.2 mmHg and 135 ± 0.5 and 81 ± 0.2 mmHg, respectively.

Conclusion. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a multifactorial condition with numerous systemic manifestations, primarily the development of cardiovascular pathology. The use of broncholytic antihypertensive pharmacotherapy in this disease - specifically the drug Berodual administered via a nebulizer inhaler - proved to be twice as effective compared to its use as a spray, and several times more effective compared to the use of phosphodiesterase inhibitors and antihistamines. Using a nebulizer inhaler in pharmacotherapy allows for faster identification of functional respiratory disorders, which contributes to recovery, a reduction in relapses, and fewer new attacks.

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